

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MEANING OF THE FORM OF ADJECTIVES AND DIMINUCTIONS IN THE UZBEKI LANGUAGE

Abdullaev Shuxrat Dauletbaevich

Karakalpak State University

candidate of philological sciences, associate professor

O‘razboyev Olimjon Rustam o‘g‘li

Karakalpak State University, master

Abstract. In this article, the forms of diminution and caress specific to nouns in the Uzbek language are analyzed. The features of the use of diminutive and caressing forms within the text are proven with concrete examples.

Key words: Uzbek language, nouns, dictionary forms, diminutive forms, caress forms.

In Uzbek linguistics, noun as one of the largest word groups has its own lexical-grammatical properties. The phenomenon of word formation and form formation in nouns is also quite extensive. It is important to analyze the phenomenon of formation of nouns and the expression of meaning in them.

The formation phenomenon is observed within independent word groups within noun and verb groups. Usually, each form of the word is formed using a special tool - an affix or auxiliary word. But in the Uzbek language, there are also forms of the word that do not have a special indicator. For example, in nouns, the plural form is formed using the affix -lar, there is no singular form: item (singular form), items (plural form), flower (singular form), flowers (plural form).

The noun group is very rich in grammatical forms. In this category, both categorical forms and non-categorical forms make up a considerable amount.

Also, there are both synthetic forms and analytical forms in the noun category. A number of categorical and non-categorical forms of the noun are formed by the affixation method. In this article, we want to focus on non-categorical forms of nouns, diminutive forms and their meaning.

In the Uzbek language literature, information is given about categorical forms rather than noun-specific forms. Non-categorical forms of nouns are almost ignored. Such forms and a number of other affixes are given as word-formers or nothing is said about them at all. Forms of this type serve to add an additional meaning to the lexical meaning of the noun, to adapt the word belonging to the noun family to a syntactic function not typical of nouns.

Diminutive and caressing forms of nouns are listed in the literature, including in the system of non-categorical forms of nouns, the diminutive form as a type of synthetic form, caressing form [1, 274], and the diminutive-caressing form as special lexical forms of the noun in the system of lexical forms, personal Forms of attitude [2, 231] are being studied in different groups.

The diminutive form of nouns is made by adding special affixes to nouns using the affixation method. With the addition of these affixes, the lexical meaning of the noun does not change, but in addition to this lexical meaning, the meanings of belittling, caressing, respecting, humiliating, strengthening, and pitying the personal attitude are loaded. These affixes include -cha, -chak, -chak, -gina (-kina, -kina), -(a)loq, -jon, -khan, -boy, -bek, -toy, -oy, -bib, -bonu, -niso, -gul and other affixes are included. We observe the meaning aspects of some of these affixes in the formation of lexical forms.

A diminutive form. The lexical form formed using the affix -cha mainly expresses the meaning of diminutive: basket, table, bird, mare, sister, stick. For example: The old man had a knot in his hand (F. Musajonov). - Because you didn't have knowledge, - says the cap (Kh. Tokhtaboyev).

-cha When the affixed form is added to words denoting a person, it can

express the meaning of respect or contempt along with caress. But these meanings are the meanings that arise from the meaning of reduction under the influence of certain facts: The leadership is done by the women Bibioysha from home (Mushtum). It's an interesting story, and I don't get bored anymore (Oybek).

Sometimes words with the suffix -cha are used to express the meaning of smallness: Vahabjan brought a small bed, it didn't work... (R. Fayziy). The bead stares into your eyes, stretches out its small white arm and tugs at your collar...(S. Zunnunova). So, it can be seen from the examples that when the suffix -cha is added to a word that expresses a small thing, it creates the meaning of diminutive, and if a diminutive determiner is used before the word of this form, it means petting together with diminutive. is also expressed.

Also, when the suffix -cha is added to living objects and the names of body parts, not only the meaning of diminutive, but also the meaning of caress arises: "If you don't mind, listen, boy", - says the old man and begins his coughing history (Oybek). The girl raised her head with hope and put it back on the pillow (M. Ismaili).

Also, the suffix -cha is added to the words expressing small things, and along with the meaning of diminution, it also expresses the attitude of the speaker to that thing, serves to mean negative or positive personal attitude. When the suffix -cha is added to words such as horse, chick, baby, a personal attitude is expressed: A horse was wading his skinny legs in the water and drinking water (from the book of tales about H. Olimjon). The baby is a boy, his eyes are like black necklaces...(From the newspaper).

It is also worth noting that the diminutive form with the affix 1) can acquire a new lexical meaning and become a new word. In this case, the meaning of diminutive is lost: like paddy field, blanket, garden (kindergarten); 2) -cha homonymous adverb and polysemous adverb.

-chak, -chak affix This affix is added to various words and expresses the meaning of diminutive, as well as caressing: mare, lamb, bride, knot. For example: He is whining about his mare, which he did not see for a day, and he stayed at home with a straw blanket (M. Muhamedov). In addition to the diminutive meaning, it can also express the personal attitude of the speaker to this or that event. The meaning of diminutive-caressing is formed by adding a different determiner before the word that receives the suffixes *-chak, -chak*, or by adding the suffix *-dek/-day* after the word of this suffix. For example: Spring came like a bride (Furqat). He was sleeping like a fed lamb (A. Qahhor).

A form of caress. *-jon* affix is added to personal nouns or proper nouns denoting a person's name to form forms expressing caressing, kissing, positive attitude: brother, father, Anvarjon. For example: My mother always oiled my shoes. My grandmother used to wipe my folder, caress her, caress her (A. Kochimov).

-khan, -oy suffixes are also added to nouns denoting a person's name and mean caressing, kissing: such as Feruza Khan, Salima Khan, Barchinoy.

It is also possible for such forms to be added to several lexical units and express different meanings in speech. In particular, it is observed that these forms are added to gender-related words in a unique way. Forms expressing the meaning of caressing can be divided into three groups according to their addition to words denoting gender and their semantic characteristics: 1) a form expressing the meaning of caressing, added to words belonging to the male and female genders; 2) a form expressing the meaning of caressing when added to words belonging to the male gender; 3) a form expressing the meaning of caressing when added to words of the female gender [3, 234].

It should also be noted that the suffixes *-jon, -khan, -oy* can become part of a person's name and become its integral component. It does not mean caressing or respecting: like Dadajon Mamajonov, Rohatoy, Onakhan, Oghiloy, Nurkhan.

In addition, such lexical forms as -gina (-kina, -kina), -lok, -boy, -bek, -kul, -toy, -beka, -bibi are added to various nouns to caress, respect, kiss. represents the nos.

On the basis of the examples and comments analyzed above, it can be said that the forms of diminutive and caressing nouns are considered an important methodological and semantic tool in the expression of a person's personal attitude, the etiquette of addressing and communicating between individuals, in the formation of speech culture, as well as as a linguistic and cultural unit.

REFERENCE

- Tursunov U., Mukhtorov J., Rahmatullayev Sh. Modern Uzbek literary language. -Tashkent, 1992. 399 p.
- Sayfullayeva R. and others. Modern Uzbek literary language. -Tashkent, 2009. 414 p.
- The team of authors. Modern Uzbek language. Volume I. Morphology. -Tashkent, 2008. 468 p.
- Dauletbayevich, A. S. (2021). The Expression of the Symbolic Phrases" to Think" in Uzbek-Karakalpak Literary Text. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(10), 57-58.
- ABDULLAYEV, S. FRAZELOGIZMLAR-MUHIM TIL BIRLIGI SIFATIDA. *АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ Учредители: Общественная организация" Институт социальной трансформации"*, 19-21.
- Abdullayev, S., & Abdullayev, O. (2023). O‘ZBEK VA QORAQALPOQ TILLARIDA IQTISODIYOT SOHASIGA DOIR ZAMONAVIY LEKSIKA. *Talqin Va Tadqiqotlar*, 1(31).
- Абдуллаев, С. (2023). Структурно-семантические особенности пословиц в узбекском и каракалпакском языках. *Американский журнал языка, грамотности и обучения в области STEM-образования (2993–2769)*, 1 (9), 70–73.
- Киличов, Н. (2022). Қадимги туркий тилдаги синоним компонентли жуфт отлар семантикаси. *Развитие лингвистики и литературоведения и образовательных технологий в эпоху глобализации*, 1(1), 40-43.
- Kilichov, N. R., & Durdona, A. (2022). Vocabulary in the old turkish language.
- Rakhmonov, N., Kurbaniyazov, M., & Kilichov, N. (2020, December). SOME NOTES ABOUT CLASSIC POETICS. In *Конференции*.
- Radjabbaevich, K. N. (2019). LINGUOAESTHETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LEXICS OF MONUMENT "OLTUN YORUG". *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 8(6), 35-42.
- Киличов, Н. Р. (2019). ЗАИМСТВОВАННАЯ ЛЕКСИКА В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИИ" ЗОЛОТОЙ БЛЕСК"(" АЛТУН ЯРУК"). In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 34-38).
- Ibragimova, Z. (2023). FORMATION OF SOCIAL COMPETENCE STUDENTS ON FOREIGN

LANGUAGE LESSONS. *Science and innovation*, 2(B6), 48-52.

Abdullaev, D. (2022). Expression of mental relationship in phraseologies.

Abdullayev, D. A. (2020). «O 'ZBEK TILINING IZOHLI LUG 'ATI» DA IBORALARNING IZOHLANISH TAMOYILLARI. *Интернаука*, (40-2), 48-50.

Kurbanbaevich, B. M. (2019). THE PHRASEMES TRANSLATED WITH THE DESCRIPTION METHOD IN THE UZBEK-KARAKALPAK LITERARY WORKS. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 8(6), 20-26.

Allambergenovich K. M. History and Tradition in the Stories of Golden Orda Literature // *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*. – 2018. – Т. 7. – №. 4. – С. 52-58.

Allambergenovich K. M., Maftuna A. Development Factors of Medieval Storytelling // *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LANGUAGE LEARNING AND APPLIED LINGUISTICS*. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 182-184.

Radjabbaevich, K. N., Allambergenovich, K. M., Dauletbaevich, A. S., Adilbayevna, K. Z., & Gulmanovna, Y. N. (2023). The Dialectal Structure of the Work "Oltun Yorug". *Telematique*, 7739-7744.

Kurbaniyozov, Makhsum Allambergenovich. "THE DIVERSITY OF THE THEME IN THE RABGHUZIY'S STORY." *Культурология, искусствоведение и филология: современные взгляды и научные исследования*. 2018. 56-59.

MASHARIPOVNA, R. K. Formation Of Correct Writing Skills. *JournalNX*, 7(02), 206-210.

Masharipovna, R. K. (2021). THE IMPORTANCE OF DICTIONARIES IN INCREASING LITERACY. *Conferencious Online*, 25-27.

Yuldashevich, O. E. (2023). The Place of Arabic Changes Related to Islam in the Linguistic Landscape of the Turkish People. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 4(7), 83-86.

Oglu, N. O. E. (2020). ETHNOGRAPHIC VOCABULARY OF UZBEK DIALECTS IN KARAKALPAKSTAN. *Евразийский Союз Ученых*, (10-4 (79)), 31-32.

Nurjanov, O. Ethnographisms Denoting Children's Games. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(1), 126-128.

Yuldashev, O. (2023). A LOOK AT THE STUDY OF FOLK PROVERBS. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(10), 47-50.

Ashirov, O. (2023). "MUQADIMAT UL-ADAB" QIPCHOQ LAHJASIGA OID QAYDLAR AKS ETGAN MUMTOZ MANBA. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(9), 164-167.

Ashirov, O. (2023). BADIY MATNLARDA NUTQIY AKT NAZARIYASIGA DOIR BA'ZI MULOHAZALAR. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(10), 27-29.

Ashirov, O. (2022). DIALEKTLARNING BADIY ASAR TILIDAGI SEMANTIK-STILISTIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 1(13), 249-252.

Allambergenova, M. (2021). O'RXUN-ENASOY OBIDALARINING O'ZBEKISTONDA

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